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APPLICATION OF MARKETING RESEARCH IN GREEN TOURISM REGIONS

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Abstract. Using the example of green tourism, the issue of applying regional marketing for the formation and promotion of a competitive tourist and recreational product is revealed. Post-crisis trends in the development of the world economy indicate the recovery of many of its sectors. One of them is the tourism and recreation sector, which, despite forecasts by world experts, in 2010 restored pre-crisis indicators. These facts open up additional prospects for the Republic of Uzbekistan as a country with tourist and recreational potential and everything necessary to form the supply of high-quality tourist and recreational products to world and domestic markets.

Key words: green tourism, regional marketing, tourist and recreational product, environmental safety, marketing strategy.

Annotatsiya. Yashil turizm misolida raqobatbardosh turistik va rekreatsion mahsulotni shakllantirish va targ'ib qilish uchun mintaqaviy marketingni qo'llash masalasi ochib beriladi. Jahon iqtisodiyotining rivojlanishidagi inqirozdan keyingi tendentsiyalar uning ko'plab sohalarining tiklanishidan dalolat beradi. Ulardan biri turizm va rekreatsion sektor bo'lib, u jahon ekspertlarining prognozlariga qaramay, 2010-yilda inqirozdan oldingi ko'rsatkichlarni tikladi. Bu faktlar O'zbekiston Respublikasi uchun turistik va rekreatsion salohiyatga ega va jahon va ichki bozorlarga yuqori sifatli turistik va rekreatsion mahsulotlar yetkazib berishni shakllantirish uchun zarur bo'lgan barcha narsalarga ega mamlakat sifatida qo'shimcha istiqbollarni ochadi.

Kalit so'zlar: yashil turizm, mintaqaviy marketing, turistik va rekreatsion mahsulot, ekologik xavfsizlik, marketing strategiyasi.

Аннотация. На примере экологического туризма рассматривается вопрос применения регионального маркетинга для формирования и продвижения конкурентоспособного туристического и рекреационного продукта. Посткризисные тенденции развития мировой экономики указывают на восстановление многих ее секторов. Одним из них является сектор туризма и отдыха, который, несмотря на прогнозы мировых экспертов, в 2010 году восстановил докризисные показатели. Эти факты открывают дополнительные перспективы для Республики Узбекистан как страны с туристическим и рекреационным потенциалом и всем необходимым для формирования предложения высококачественных туристических и рекреационных продуктов на мировом и внутреннем рынках.

Ключевые слова: экологический туризм, региональный маркетинг, туристический и рекреационный продукт, экологическая безопасность, маркетинговая стратегия.

INTRODUCTION

Green tourism, or ecotourism, has been growing and developing rapidly in recent years around the world. This type of tourism aims to ensure environmental sustainability while utilizing natural resources, creating benefits for local communities, and providing tourists with the opportunity to preserve natural beauty and cultural heritage. Along with the development of green tourism, marketing in this sector is also gaining importance. Through marketing research, there are opportunities to improve the effectiveness of green tourism, make tourist destinations more attractive, and develop new strategies.

Marketing research, in turn, includes scientific methods aimed at in-depth analysis of tourism requirements, consumer behavior, and market competition. The application of marketing research in green tourism destinations is crucial for promoting ecotourism and ensuring the sustainable use of natural resources. Today, many tourist destinations are developing marketing strategies to develop their green tourism potential, which in turn will bring economic, environmental, and social benefits.

The purpose of the article is to study the role and importance of marketing research in green tourism areas, as well as to identify new approaches to tourism development. The study analyzes green tourism marketing strategies, successful experiences and practices in this area. It also examines the problems and solutions that arise in the development of eco-tourism.

The main task of this article is to provide a comprehensive analysis of the significant changes that green tourism and marketing are bringing about, their role in maintaining environmental and economic sustainability worldwide, as well as how these processes can be made more effective with the help of marketing research.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Analysis of major studies and publications shows that most scientists focus their attention on individual theoretical aspects without studying the specifics of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Thus, international experts give theoretical recommendations on the application of marketing in this area F. Kotler, I. Zorin, and some emphasize from the point of view of existing recreational resources M. Nudelman. The issue of developing the tourism market of the Republic of Uzbekistan has not been overlooked by domestic researchers A.M. Abduvokhidov, A.A. Eshtayev, M.T. Aliyeva, S.R. Safaeva, A.N. Norchayev, Kh.F. Ochilova, and others, who reveal individual aspects of the problem. At the same time, there are no comprehensive, systematic studies on the use of regional marketing for the formation of a competitive tourism and recreational product of our country and the development of green tourism in domestic and world markets.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The purpose of the study is to analyze the effectiveness of marketing strategies in the field of green tourism and identify methods for implementing these strategies in practice. The methodology of the study consists of the following main stages: The existing scientific literature, articles and other scientific sources on green tourism and marketing strategies were studied. At this stage, the main attention is paid to the marketing basis of eco-tourism, innovative approaches and their effectiveness. The main method of the study is a qualitative approach (qualitative research). Through this approach, data on the marketing characteristics and activities of green tourism are qualitatively analyzed. Indeed, if one of the elements of the structure of the economic mechanism of nature management is the objective economic interests of nature users, then the form of the economic mechanism of this area is the stimulation of environmental protection activities, through which the economic interests of the subjects of economic relations of nature management are realized.. It is planned to use interviews, questionnaires and expert assessments. The empirical part of the study will be carried out in existing green tourism regions. In this part, the practical manifestations of marketing activities and strategies of selected regions will be studied. In this case, the effectiveness of marketing strategies will be determined using questionnaires and interviews to collect information on the studied regions. The data collected during the study will be studied through statistical analysis. The interrelationships and results of the data obtained in this process are visually displayed using drawings and diagrams. Based on the results of the study, the effectiveness of marketing strategies and existing problems in green tourism areas and their solutions are determined. The study develops new proposals and methods. At the same time, the article provides a comprehensive analysis of the application of marketing research in green tourism and its impact on regional development. When implementing the methodological approach, special attention is paid to avoiding methodological errors and obtaining accurate, reliable results.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

Today, our country's national tourism and recreation product and tourism and recreation product offered by market entities. There are interrelationships and differences between these concepts. Considering the definitions of scholars, we formulate the essence of a local tourism and recreational product as a complex concept consisting of numerous interconnected components of tourism and recreational services provided by individual market entities. Therefore, the established quality standards for the production and consumption of tourist and recreational products are, first of all, characteristic of all its components.

The competitiveness of national products in this area depends on the state image, environmental safety, infrastructure development, transport network, and the level of service quality of all market entities participating in the process. At the same time, improving the quality indicators of one of the service providers cannot simultaneously affect their quality for all other entities. Therefore, for the effective formation of the national product, it is necessary for the state to implement strategic planning, direct efforts towards improving the overall awareness of all participants and the quality of service provision for each individual entity. Thus, the components of the tourism and recreation industry are the hotel industry, financial institutions, transport, communications, information and communication facilities, as well as other sectors engaged in the production of goods and the provision of services for tourists and vacationers. This should indeed be the country's strategic direction, since other countries are competitors with their tourism and recreational products, identity, and level of service. One of the first steps in solving this problem is marketing research, which can answer the following questions:

Marketing research of the tourism and recreation market (Fig. 1).¹

Taking into account the existing tourist and recreational resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to emphasize their uniqueness and thereby give our local product a competitive advantage. It should be noted that this can only be achieved through the efforts of its individual subjects. For this, first of all, it is necessary to carry out informational and educational work with tour operators who offer tours to Uzbekistan for end consumers. In our opinion, an effective marketing tool for promoting Uzbekistan as a provider of high-quality tourist and recreational services (including green tourism) should be the marketing of regions at the macro, meso, local, and micro levels. This is systematic work in the interests of the regions, their internal subjects, as well as external objects that are in the region's focus.

Since these areas are very interconnected, it is necessary to take into account their interaction. Thus, the marketing situation throughout the country can be represented as a set of marketing situations in the regions. There is a similarity inherent in the national tourism and recreational product as a set of tourism and recreational services of all its constituent entities. Therefore, the specificity of marketing areas is their complexity, because if the area where they are located is depressed, they do not have the objective opportunity to carry out successful marketing activities at the city level.

According to the Russian scientist-marketer A.P. Pankrukhin, the main arguments in favor of the country are:

- 1) improving the standard of living and well-being of citizens and companies;
- 2) political stability;
- 3) creation of qualified internal demand;
- 4) promising and understandable goals and strategies;
- 5) the prevalence of modern methods of organizing enterprises and a high level of management;
- 6) growth of investments in domestic production by local residents;
- 7) active state policy aimed at supporting these changes in ensuring the openness of the country's economy, including for international competition.

Taking into account the above recommendations, our state should focus its efforts on their implementation. Of course, this list is incomplete, as it raises questions about the quality of these services and the level of service provision of enterprises. When developing a marketing strategy for the creation and promotion of a tourist and recreational product of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the world market, it is necessary to take into account the latest trends in its development, in particular: reducing the duration of travel, increasing the share of young people and the elderly in the tourist structure, and focusing on these market segments.

Taking into account the specifics of regional marketing, it requires focusing on the needs of target groups of consumers of regional services, as well as creating competitive advantages for customer profitability compared to other regions. At the same time, several concepts of «regional product» form the basis of regional marketing strategies, the implementation of which increases attractiveness and the number of tourists and vacationers (Fig. 2). As a rule, it is at this level that you can start considering green tourism, since it has its own characteristics that distinguish it as a separate product.

1 Muallif ishlanmasi

(Fig. 2) Conceptual components of the tourist and recreational product²

When considering the national tourist and recreational product from the point of view of conceptual components, it is necessary to pay special attention to each individual region, to develop a program of cooperation between central and local authorities for the development of comprehensive programs to stimulate individual regions, ecologically attractive zones. In addition, it is necessary to actively participate in all international events aimed at popularizing the tourist and recreational products of the participating states.

Local marketing of regions, that is, cities and settlements, also requires some attention. Its influence is manifested in ensuring the attractiveness of the city, increasing its image and prestige; increasing the attractiveness of the financial, labor, social, material, technical, and other resources concentrated in the city, attracting state and other external orders and investments into the city. The strategy for increasing the tourist and recreational attractiveness of cities consists of the following stages:

1. Designing an attractive location and image. This stage begins, first of all, with the study of the natural, cultural, and historical features of the territory, the analysis of its strengths and weaknesses, and the identification of threats and opportunities. In addition, an important element of this stage is the analysis of the situation in the field of tourism and recreation and the identification of the target audience and competitors. The task of managing the strategic image is also more important: its study, segmentation and creation of attractive components of the image of a particular territory, taking into account the image created in different audiences, the requirements of the target audience, and the dissemination of information about them.

2. Creation of tourist incentives.

3. Creation of a service system that meets the needs of tourists and vacationers. The last two steps include stimulating the activities of hotels, restaurants, cafes, transport networks, manufacturers and sellers of souvenirs; production of diagrams, maps, reference books, calendar events; organization of information bureaus; conducting explanatory and promotional work with the urban population, especially with service sector employees.

4. Promotion of attractive advertising opportunities in the press, on radio and television; direct marketing; Internet; event marketing and the use of a wide range of PR tools are of great importance.

The implementation of these steps will help strengthen the position of any region among both foreign and domestic tourists and vacationers.

The last component of regional marketing is place marketing at the micro level. According to the founder of marketing, F. Kotler, this is an activity carried out with the aim of creating, maintaining, or changing attitudes or behavior towards certain places. These include marketing of places of economic activity, recreation, housing, and investment. At this stage, competitors become not only foreign but also local entities, neighboring institutions, and other market entities providing similar services.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, the implementation of a regional marketing strategy can become a driving force for the formation of a high-quality national product for the Republic of Uzbekistan, the popularization of green tourism both within the country and abroad. At the same time, it serves to increase the level and quality of service of all tourist and recreational services, which allows solving the problems of realizing the existing resource potential, ensuring employment, developing infrastructure, attracting investments, and increasing budget revenues at all levels.

² Muallif ishlanmasi

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